

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF BILINGUALISM ON APHASIA RECOVERY: PATTERNS, COMPARISONS, AND COGNITIVE CONTRIBUTIONS

Hamamah Ansari^{*1}, Fatima Yousuf², Hafeez Punjani³

¹hamamahansari@gmail.com, ²fatima.yousuf@zu.edu.pk, ³hafeez.punjani@zu.edu.pk

Corresponding Author: *

Hamamah Ansari

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ABSTRACT

Background of the study: This study aims to review the current literature on aphasia treatment in bilingual individuals, it gives an insight for speech-language pathologists (SLPs) to plan informed therapeutic decisions. It focuses on how recovery from aphasia is positively influenced by bilingualism, examining the impact of language choice and usage on recovery patterns. The study also discusses the differences in recovery between bilingual and monolingual individuals with aphasia, highlighting the significant role linguistic and cognitive factors play in the experiences of bilingual aphasia patients.

Methodology: A comprehensive review of available literature from PubMed and Google Scholar was conducted, focused on studies addressing the treatment and intervention of bilingual patients with aphasia. The selected resources were analyzed to study the current therapeutic strategies and outcomes for bilingual individuals with aphasia.

Results: Bilingual individuals with aphasia often exhibit less severe symptoms and demonstrate better performance in language tasks compared to monolinguals. Their recovery is shaped by language-specific neural pathways and focused rehabilitation efforts, highlighting the need for personalized therapeutic approaches for bilingual patients.

Conclusion: Individuals with bilingual aphasia demonstrate improved performance in therapeutic tasks such as language tasks. The recovery patterns depend on tailored therapeutic approaches for intervention.

Keywords: Multilingualism, Aphasia, Executive Function, Semantics, Ischemic Stroke, Language Therapy, Cognition, Neuronal Plasticity

1. INTRODUCTION

Bilingualism, can be define as the ability to speak or use two languages with varying degrees of proficiency, it provodes cognitive and linguistic advantages to individuals. With approximately half of the global population being bilingual or multilingual, the impact of neurological disorders, such as stroke and traumatic brain injury, can affect multiple languages in bilingual speakers. The recovery of aphasia, a language disorder often resulting from such neurological conditions, is

influenced by various factors, including lesion-related and aphasia-related aspects. (1)

In chronic aphasia, several predictors have been identified to contribute to positive recovery outcomes, independent of each other. Factors such as higher education, smaller lesion size, younger age, and current antidepressant use have been associated with improved recovery in individuals with aphasia. These predictors play a significant role in shaping the rehabilitation process and outcomes for patients with

language impairments post-stroke or brain injury. (2)

Administering language therapy to bilingual individuals with aphasia poses distinctive obstacles in contrast to treating monolingual individuals. These challenges surpass logistical concerns, such as obtaining bilingual evaluation and therapy resources and locating proficient bilingual speech-language pathologists (SLPs) or pairing two SLPs skilled in the required languages. A major conceptual dilemma emerges regarding whether to prioritize one language or integrate both languages into therapy. The researchers of bilingual intervention debate that including both languages enables individuals with aphasia to utilize all available communication methods, similar to how gestures or writing are used to support verbal communication. (3)

This literature review seeks to comprehensively analyze and evaluate the existing data on aphasia treatment in bilingual individuals. By integration of available information, this review aims to provide speech-language pathologists (SLPs) with valuable comprehension to create optimal therapeutic decisions when working with bilingual patients with aphasia. Additionally, it anticipates to highlight the empirical strength of the current evidence, identifying any gaps or limitations in the research. It also highlights the areas that required further investigation. This review aims to contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the field of bilingual aphasia treatment.

1. The recovery from aphasia is positively impacted by being bilingual.

In 2016 a group of scientists found no discrepancy in aphasia frequency between monolinguals and bilinguals among 608 ischemic stroke patients (4). However, twice as many bilinguals exhibited normal cognition post-stroke, potentially linked to heightened cognitive results. Faroqi Shah and coworkers investigated 38 aphasia patients, revealing superior conversational skills in bilinguals correlated with enhanced executive functions compared to monolinguals. Despite lower overall cognitive control in aphasia patients compared to age-matched controls, bilinguals still showed advantages in two out of three

tasks, supporting the notion of bilingual inhibitory control advantage. (3)

According to Durjoy Lahiri and colleagues the study was conducted on 208 patients, in which 120 were monolingual and 43 were bilingual speakers. Bilinguals showed a higher likelihood of recovery compared to monolinguals, particularly evident in sub-cortical and mixed cortico-subcortical strokes. Across genders, bilingual patients, particularly males, exhibited superior recovery. Additionally, bilinguals displayed notably greater improvement in aphasia quotient (AQ) in certain subgroups, including low age, high volume, and low initial AQ. (5)

2. The recovery patterns in bilingual individuals experiencing aphasia are positively influenced by their choices and usage of language.

The literature on bilingual and multilingual speakers with aphasia identifies two patterns of language deficit and recovery: parallel and nonparallel. In parallel patterns, all languages show similar deficits and recover at similar rates, whereas in nonparallel patterns, one language may recover faster or be less affected. Theories propose neural and psychological mechanisms underlying these patterns and variables determining language advantage. The case study was conducted on a 57 years old male, highly proficient Russian-Hebrew language bilingual speaker who had left CVA. He was diagnosed with Receptive and Expressive aphasia in both languages. In the course of the intervention program, he received therapy initially in Hebrew language then Russian language. When he was reassessed post onset of stroke, it was concluded that receiving therapy in one language has a positive effect on both treated and non-treated language. Significant improvement was shown in auditory comprehension. (6)

Marco Calabria, Nicholas Grunden, Mariona Serra, Carmen García-Sánchez and Albert Cost in 2019 investigated semantic processing in bilinguals, focusing on language dependency. They found bilinguals with fluent aphasia and parallel language impairment underwent assessment in production and comprehension tasks across both languages. Additionally, an executive control (EC) task was utilized to

investigate potential overlaps between linguistic and non-linguistic control mechanisms. Three key findings emerged: 1) Semantic control processes linked to lexical selection exhibited language dependency, seen through a greater semantic interference effect in non-dominant language production among bilingual aphasic patients. 2) The retrieval of semantic representations demonstrated some language dependency, especially within dual language contexts. 3) Linguistic processes of semantic control only partially intersected with domain-general EC, notably during conflict monitoring.(7)

Saskia Mooijman, Rob Schoonen, Ardi Roelofs & Marina B. Ruiters 2024 studied voluntarily mixing language is beneficial for bilingual with Aphasia (BWA) leading to mixing benefits and providing a way to circumvent word retrieval difficulty to discover the possible advantages of language mixing through (a) Analyzing costs associated with voluntary and cued language mixing, b) Contrasting costs of voluntary and cued language switching,(c) Investigating the connection between ease of lexical retrieval and voluntary language selection and investigate the correlation among cued between-language switching costs and intra-language switching abilities. The study involving Dutch (L1) and either German or English (L2) speakers with aphasia, patients exhibited a greater decline in proficiency in their L2 compared to their L1, showing better performance in task switching activities and faster naming in a single language. Voluntary language switches were more pronounced, but there was no statistical sample was reported for differences or associations between switch costs in-between and within language switching.(8)

3. Recovery patterns contrast between bilingual aphasia and monolingual aphasia.

There are six distinct recovery patterns of language among bilingual patients with aphasia according to the studies that might occur following deficits in different languages. These include:

1. Parallel recovery: The language primarily used before aphasia remains stronger than others

2. Differential recovery: The language less frequently used before aphasia showed better recovery compared to the dominant language.

3. Antagonistic recovery: As the less dominant language improves, the dominant language used before the onset of aphasia fades away.

4. Alternating antagonism: Language dominance fluctuates between languages during the recovery process.

5. Blended recovery: Absence of language dominance results in the interchangeable use of two or more languages.

6. Selective and successive recovery: The recovery of one language is succeeded by the recovery of another language or languages.

These patterns suggest that the extent and manner of recovery can vary significantly across languages and individuals, highlighting the complex nature of language deficits and rehabilitation.(9)

A patient with left-hemispheric stroke, the patient was bilingual, fluent in German and French language underwent Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) to assess language recovery during picture naming tasks in both languages. After 32 months, selective recovery in German naming ability was observed, correlating with increased brain activation compared to French. Additional short-term intensive language training further improved German naming, revealing bilateral neuroplasticity reorganization but no enhancement in French. In pre-training, German naming activated a predominantly right-hemispheric network, while French activation was confined to occipital and fronto-parietal regions with less frontal involvement. German naming exhibited heightened activation in right superior temporal sulcus (STS) and middle temporal gyrus (MTG), mirroring the lesion left-hemispheric areas. Post-training, German naming additionally engaged bilateral fronto-temporal areas, while no changes were noted in French. Therapy showed increased activation in frontal and parietal regions, primarily for German naming, indicating a language-specific effect on brain activation patterns influenced by rehabilitation efforts focused on German language skills.(1)

The recovery trajectories in bilingual aphasia diverge from those in monolingual aphasia,

potentially due to milder aphasia, heightened alertness, strengthened cognitive control, and superior executive functions in bilingual individuals. These differences underscore the intricate relationship between bilingualism and aphasia recovery, implying distinct benefits and obstacles encountered by bilingual individuals during post-stroke language rehabilitation. (5)

4. In the experiences of bilingual individuals with aphasia, linguistic and cognitive factors play a significant role.

There are essential linguistic and cognitive elements influencing individuals with aphasia who are bilingual encompass those non-native English-speaking bilinguals with aphasia exhibited inferior performance on language assessments paralleled to monolingual control counterparts, likely attributed to limited pre-morbid language proficiency. (5). The rehabilitation course for each language in bilingual aphasia pivots on factors such as the age of language acquisition, frequency of language exposure, and prior proficiency (10). Bilingual individuals with aphasia often exhibit enhanced alertness, conversational abilities, and executive functions compared to their monolingual counterparts. They may also demonstrate benefits in tasks requiring inhibitory and cognitive control, potentially contributing to their improved performance in expressive language tasks. (11). There were few studies in which neuroanatomical differences between bilinguals and monolinguals may impact language processing, with bilinguals having more distinct brain regions for each language. The impairment to specific areas like frontal-basal ganglia circuits can lead to selective recovery or impairment of one language in bilingual aphasia. Additionally, bilingual individuals with aphasia might show distinctive recovery patterns, including pathological language switching and mixing, possibly due to deficits in language control mechanisms. (12)

DISCUSSION:

Speech language pathologists (SLP) objective is to accurately discriminate between communication disorders and normal linguistic variations when assessing and treating bilingual post-stroke aphasia patients. Their aim is to create treatment strategies that effectively

promote linguistic recovery and minimize the functional impact of the disorder (ASHA). This literature review sought to investigate whether individuals with aphasia tend to exhibit superior performance in their first-acquired (L1) language compared to a later-learned (L2) language. Furthermore, the study aimed to explore the factors in bilingual aphasia patients that impact recovery, including the influence of being bilingual and recovery patterns in bilingual individuals experiencing aphasia, which may be positively influenced by their language choices and usage. It also discussed the discrimination in recovery patterns between bilingual aphasia and monolingual aphasia, additionally the roles of linguistic and cognitive factors in this context. According to the literature, Bilingual aphasia patients tend to exhibit less severe aphasia symptoms compared to monolingual aphasia patients. (5) Bilingual individuals with aphasia often demonstrate superior performance in language tasks, particularly in conversational skills, which is associated with enhanced executive functions compared to monolinguals(13). Studies have found that bilingual aphasia patients have a higher probability of recovering compared to monolinguals, especially in cases of subcortical and mixed cortico-subcortical strokes However, one study found no difference in aphasia frequency between monolinguals and bilinguals (5). The literature on bilingual individuals with aphasia outlines two recovery patterns: parallel and nonparallel. Case studies, like one involving a 57-year-old proficient in Russian-Hebrew bilingualism, indicate that therapy in one language can positively affect both treated and untreated languages, notably improving auditory comprehension. (6). Semantic processing in bilinguals with aphasia reveals language-specific control in lexical selection and retrieval, alongside intersections with domain-general executive functions, notably during conflict monitoring. (7). Faster lexical retrieval in a single language, emphasizing more pronounced voluntary language switches without significant differences in switch costs between interlanguage and intra-language switching.(11). The recovery patterns in bilingual aphasia vary, reflecting the complex interplay between language-specific neural mechanisms and rehabilitation efforts. Case

studies suggest that selective recovery in the dominant language, with intensive training showing language-specific effects on neuroplasticity reorganization. Contrasts with monolingual aphasia underscore the unique challenges and advantages for bilingual individuals during rehabilitation, emphasizing the importance of tailored therapeutic approaches for optimal outcomes. (1) Bilinguals may exhibit enhanced cognitive functions compared to monolinguals, impacting their rehabilitation course. Neuroanatomical differences and deficits in language control mechanisms can contribute to distinctive recovery patterns, including pathological language switching. (Łuczyńska 2011)

CONCLUSION:

Bilingual individuals with aphasia often exhibit milder symptoms and superior performance in language tasks compared to monolinguals, the recovery pattern influenced by language-specific neural mechanisms and rehabilitation efforts, underscoring the need for tailored therapeutic approaches.

DISCLAIMER:

This literature review is created on publicly available sources. The analysis and conclusions made are solely based on authors.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

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